

Physico-Chemical Studies on Some West Bengal Soils under Waterlogged Condition. Part I

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The effect of submergence on the oxidised mineral components of two nearly neutral cultivated soils (both surface and sub-surface samples) and of two virgin acid soils of West Bengal has been studied. It has been found that in Darjeeling acid soil, the reducing condition developed as a result of submergence is more intense while the neutral soils undergo the least reduction. In the sub-surface samples the release of soluble iron is delayed and some inactive forms of manganese are found to be slowly converted into the reducible forms and are thus brought to the labile pool. It appears that the initial organic matter content is primarily responsible for creating reducing condition and as a consequence of it, greater mobilisation of iron and manganese and some reduction of sulphates were noticed. The extent of mobilisations of iron and manganese however, depends upon the pH, original contents of the free oxides and also on the duration of submergence.

RECENT studies have shown that flooding brings about distinct changes in the physical, chemical and biological soil environment of growing plants. Chemically, this condition is characterized by low oxygen tension and high carbon dioxide concentration, virtual absence of sulphate and nitrate and simultaneous accumulation of ammonia, large amount of reduced iron or manganese compounds and various products of anaerobic decomposition of organic matter present in soil. The reduction of typical soil component to their reduced counterparts is brought about by bacterial metabolites^{1,2} as well as by direct reduction coupled with respiration^{3,4}.

Ponnampereuma *et al.*^{5,6} studied the kinetics of iron and manganese transformations in the soil solution of flooded soils and attempted to draw a quantitative correlation among the physical quantities like Eh, pH, $p\text{CO}_2$ and the activities of reduced ions using appropriate equations for each system whose presence in soil was assumed on thermodynamic and chemical grounds. Patrick and Turner⁷ studied the effect of redox potential on manganese transformation in water-logged soil. Earlier Mandal⁸ studied the degree of chemical transformation of iron and manganese in some waterlogged rice soils.

In first part of our present investigation experiments were conducted to study the effect of submergence on the mobilisation of two extremely important metallic plant nutrients, *viz.*, iron and manganese in two nearly neutral and two acid soils of West Bengal. Two more samples of the sub-surface horizon of the neutral cultivated soils were also included in the experiment in order to ascertain any difference in behaviour between the surface and sub-surface horizon. Total oxidizable matter present

in those soils and their variation along with the period of submergence were determined which served as a measure of the capacity factor of the overall reduced state of the soil concerned at a particular stage. Soluble sulphate was another mineral constituent which was estimated in order to find out any reduction of this component in a waterlogged soil. Such chemical transformations have immense importance in the field of soil-plant relationship, especially from the nutritional point of view of semi-aquatic plants such as rice.

Experimental

Soils: The neutral soils were collected from the cultivated paddy field of Kankjole and Kamarpole in the district of 24-Parganas from 0-14 and 15-30 cm depth. The acid soils were collected from Rydak Tea Estate, Eastern Doars, Jalpaiguri and Ging Tea State, Darjeeling respectively from the top 15 cm layer of virgin lands. The soils were air-dried under shade, ground and sieved through a 0.2 mm sieve. Some physico-chemical properties of the soils necessary for an understanding of the results of the present experiment are shown in Table 1.

Procedure: 50 g of each soil were taken in a series of 250 ml polythene beakers. The soils were saturated with de-mineralised water by stirring and excess water was poured in upto a height of 2.5 cm from the surface of soils. The level of water was maintained constant during the entire period of submergence by the addition of requisite quantity of de-mineralised water at frequent intervals.

In the present investigation two sets of beakers were used, one for incubating the soil for a period of 15 days and the other for 30 days, both under

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SOILS UNDER INVESTIGATION

Srl. No.	Name of the soils	Org. carbon (%)	pH	Conductivity (mmhos/cm)	Free ion oxide (%)	Extractable iron (mg/100 g of soil)	Active manganese (mg/100 g of soil)
1.	Kamarpole soil (0-15 cm)	0.57	6.70	0.720	1.58	0.11	21.00
2.	Kamarpole soil (15-30 cm)	0.40	6.90	1.260	1.38	—	4.60
3.	Kankjole soil (0-15 cm)	0.64	6.60	0.270	2.37	0.28	15.60
4.	Kankjole soil (15-30 cm)	0.41	7.15	0.340	1.97	—	11.20
5.	Jalpaiguri soil (0-15 cm)	2.03	4.40	0.495	1.48	0.24	6.15
6.	Darjeeling soil (0-15 cm)	2.27	4.70	0.740	3.56	0.40	22.10

submerged condition. Duplicates were run for each set of experimental studies. Wet soil samples were collected as quickly as possible with a spoon head spatula after pipetting out the supernatant liquid avoiding much agitation of soil for the purpose of chemical analysis or physico-chemical measurements. Analysis were carried out also with the supernatant liquids for chemical constituents like iron and manganese.

Measurement of pH: 10 g of wet soil were taken in a beaker, a 1 : 1 (on dry-weight basis of the soil) suspension of it was prepared in de-mineralised water and pH was measured after standardisation of the pH meter (Systronics : type—301-1) at pH 4.0 using standard buffers. For the supernatant liquid, pH was measured immediately after its collection with the help of a pipette.

Estimation of iron: 10 g of wet soil were taken in a 250 ml conical flask and on dry-weight basis a measured volume of 1.0 N ammonium acetate (adjusted to pH 3.0) was added to give the soil : extractant ratio of 1 : 10. After thorough mixing it was filtered and an aliquot was taken from the filtrate for the colorimetric determination of iron by the ortho-phenanthroline method as described by Jackson⁹. A Spectronics-20 (Bausch and Lomb) spectrophotometer was used for all colorimetric measurements. The amount of iron obtained by this method included exchangeable Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺ and dilute acid soluble iron.

Iron was also determined in an aliquot of supernatant liquid collected by carefully pipetting out the standing water from the beaker.

Estimation of manganese: Manganese was estimated colorimetrically by the periodate method after extracting the wet soil samples with 1.0 N ammonium acetate solution containing 0.2% of hydroquinone. The procedure followed was same as described by Jackson⁹. Manganese determined by the above method was represented as "active manganese" because it included all the three important forms of manganese, viz., the reducible, exchangeable and water soluble ones. Manganese was also determined in the supernatant liquid.

Determination of total oxidisable matter: 10 g of wet soil were extracted with Morgan's solution using a soil-extractant ratio of 1 : 5 as followed by Dev and Sharma¹⁰. The oxidisable matter in the soil extract was determined by a method prescribed by the American Public Health Association¹¹ for the estimation of the oxygen consuming capacity of sewage. The results were expressed in terms of ml of 0.01 N KMnO₄ consumed.

Determination of sulphates: The sulphates were determined in the ammonium acetate extract of the wet soils by turbidimetric method as recommended by Bardsley *et al.*¹² and Black¹³.

Results and Discussion

The ammonium acetate (buffered to pH 3) extractable iron increased in all the soil samples with duration of submergence. The changes in extractable iron of soils and soluble iron contents of supernatant liquids are given in Table 2. The results are also

TABLE 2—CHANGES IN EXTRACTABLE IRON OF SOILS AND SOLUBLE IRON OF SUPERNATANT SOLUTIONS

Sample No.	Fe in original soil (mg/100 g of soil)*	15 days incubation		30 days incubation	
		Fe in soil (mg/100 g of soil)*	Fe in supernatant solution (ppm)	Fe in soil (mg/100 g of soil)*	Fe in supernatant solution (ppm)
1	0.11	0.17	3.60	0.30	3.10
2	—	Trace	0.86	0.01	2.00
3	0.28	0.42	6.40	0.70	5.40
4	—	Trace	1.60	0.04	5.00
5	0.24	0.17	0.13	0.55	0.23
6	0.40	70.20	55.00	301.70	330.00

* Values are given on oven-dry weight basis.

shown graphically in Fig. 1. It appears from the graph that the dissolution of the soluble ferric iron compounds in soils continued throughout the entire period of submergence. Except in soil No. 5, release of extractable iron was enhanced in all soils with increase in the level of organic matter. The increase is found to be highest in the Darjeeling acid soil.

Although the faster rate of decomposition of organic matter is expected at higher pH, the initial content of organic matter present in the soils largely determine the mobilisation of iron by chelation and subsequent reduction. The increased reducing condition set up through submergence evidently increased the ferrous iron content but the total amount of such soluble form of iron will depend upon the amount of free oxides of iron present in the soil. This is reflected in the significantly higher content of soluble iron

analysis of the supernatant solutions is well-correlated with the increase in pH of the respective soils.

TABLE 3—CHANGES IN ACTIVE MANGANESE OF SOILS AND SOLUBLE MANGANESE OF SUPERNATANT SOLUTIONS

Sample No.	Mn in original soil (mg/100 g of soil)*	15 days incubation		30 days incubation	
		Mn in soil* (mg/100 g of soil)*	Mn in supernatant solution (ppm)	Mn in soil (mg/100 g of soil)*	Mn in supernatant solution (ppm)
1	21.00	19.84	—	15.64	—
2	4.60	7.10	—	6.37	—
3	15.60	14.28	—	13.97	—
4	11.20	15.80	—	11.00	—
5	6.15	4.92	Trace	5.54	—
6	22.10	24.65	3.00	36.84	16.75

* Values are given on oven dry weight basis.

Fig. 1.

— Surface soil O Kamarpole Soil
 - - - Sub-surface soil Δ Kankjole Soil
 - - - Supernatant liquid X Jalpaiguri Soil

obtained in soil No. 6 which is rich in organic matter and at the same time contains a high amount of free iron oxides. In case of surface samples of the neutral soil (1 and 3) the concentration of iron in supernatant solutions did not change any further on prolonging the period of submergence; rather it showed a decreasing tendency while the concentration of iron in the supernatant solutions of the sub-surface soils (Nos. 2 and 4) increased markedly. This indicates that the peak period of accumulation of water soluble iron was attained earlier in surface soils than in the case of sub-surface soils. Iron in the subsurface soils was perhaps in a more difficultly reducible form. The decreasing tendency of iron mobilisation in the supernatant solutions of the surface soils is not unexpected since after the peak reduction period, the high pH of these soils becomes quite favourable for the oxidation and subsequent precipitation of iron as hydrous oxides, sulphides or carbonates. On the other hand, the low pH of the acid soils will keep the iron in largely reduced and soluble forms for a longer period of time.

The pH changes of the submerged soil which is believed to be associated with the reduction of iron and manganese has been recorded in Table 5. The extent of mobilisation of iron, as evident from the

A continuous decrease of active manganese was observed in the neutral surface soils. In the corresponding sub-surface samples the amount of active manganese increased upto 15 days of submergence after which there was a decreasing trend. Submergence has evidently converted some relatively inert manganese compounds of the subsurface soils into the active forms. The results are shown in Table 3. The trend of such changes can be observed also from the Fig. 2.

Fig. 2.

— Surface soil O Kamarpole soil
 - - - Sub-surface soil Δ Kankjole soil
 - - - Supernatant liquid X Jalpaiguri soil
 O Darjeeling soil.

The decrease in active manganese may be attributed to the chemical oxidation of Mn(II) in presence of organic hydroxy acids by the oxygen from the air

at pH 7 and above. The oxidation is commenced at the surface layer and the active manganese present in the soil is converted into the inactive state. The results are in conformity with the observations of Takkar¹⁴ and Heintze and Mann¹⁵.

The continuous increase in active manganese in acid soils may be due to the effect of reducing acids produced in the decomposition of organic matter at low pH. The results are in agreement with the observations of Takkar¹⁴ and Heintze and Mann¹⁵ who found that hydroxy acids dissolved relatively inactive manganese oxides such as MnO₂ at low pH.

In supernatant solutions of all the neutral soil samples manganese was practically absent which indicates that it was largely present in the reducible forms and the manganese if reduced at all, were either fixed in the colloidal complex or reoxidized into the difficultly reducible forms at the higher pH prevailing in those soils. In Darjeeling acid soil (No. 6) the larger amounts of manganese present in the supernatant solution is obviously due to the low pH which prevented the chemical oxidation of manganese to higher states.

The amount of ammonium acetate extractable sulphate decreased at the earlier stages of submergence in all the soils. The decrease is mostly due to the dilution of the system, soluble sulphates going into the supernatant solutions. On extending the submergence upto 30 days, all the neutral soils showed a further decrease in their sulphate content while in the acid soil (No. 5), no such change was observed. It seems (Table 4) that in the neutral

TABLE 4—CHANGES IN EXTRACTABLE SULPHATES OF SUBMERGED SOILS

Sample No.	Original soil (ppm)	15 days incubation (ppm)	30 days incubation (ppm)
1	22.0	8.0	5.6
2	50.0	20.2	11.3
3	16.0	5.5	—
4	14.0	Trace	—
5	24.0	8.5	8.5
6	—	—	—

soils some reduction of sulphates occurred under submerged condition but in acid soils no such reduction could take place, possibly, because of the acid sensitivity of the sulphate reducers.

TABLE 5—CHANGES IN pH OF THE SOILS

Sample No.	Original soil	15 days incubation	30 days incubation
1	6.70	6.95	6.80
2	6.90	7.25	7.00
3	6.60	6.80	6.70
4	7.15	7.20	7.00
5	4.40	5.00	5.15
6	4.70	6.10	6.60

The values for the total oxidisable matter at different periods of incubation have been presented in Table 6. In soils 1 and 3, the total oxidisable matter remained almost unchanged for a considerable period but there was a marked decrease on extending the submergence to 30 days. For the latter soils the reduced products, both organic and inorganic, accumulated during the initial stages of incubation after which the reduced organic products might have decreased leaving the reduced inorganic substances like Fe²⁺, Mn²⁺ and S²⁻.

TABLE 6—CHANGES IN TOTAL OXIDISABLE MATTER (ml of 0.01N KMnO₄ per 10 g of soil)

Sample No.	Original soil	15 days incubation	30 days incubation
1	6.60	6.30	1.61
2	1.20	0.32	1.77
3	3.60	3.65	1.27
4	1.80	0.31	1.10
5	20.80	24.00	9.80
6	84.00	87.70	100.00

In the corresponding sub-surface soils the reduced products accumulated at a later period of submergence because of the comparatively slower rate of decomposition of the organic matter and the relatively slow release of the reduced inorganic species. For the acid soil (No. 6) increasing oxidisable matter may be partly correlated with the increase in soluble iron and manganese. In the other acid soil (No. 5) the reduced organic fraction of the oxidisable matter markedly decreased while the reduced inorganic species did not increase proportionately with continued submergence. Since the nature of the reduced organic fraction which constitute the bulk of the oxidisable matter is not yet fully known, any attempt to correlate it as a capacity factor for the reducing condition with other observations may be erroneous.

An understanding of the chemical transformations in submerged soils is extremely essential for the maintenance of a favourable reducing condition in low lying paddy fields because the reduced inorganic ions, viz., Mn²⁺, Fe²⁺, S²⁻, etc. and the various organic acids produced in course of the anaerobic decomposition of the organic matter, if accumulated in excess of the toxic level, will be harmful instead of being beneficial to the growing plants. The knowledge of the chemistry of submerged soil will also help in explaining any change in the physical condition of the submerged soil and the soil forming processes as modified by the drastic action of waterlogging.

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